

Integrating Quantitative Mapping into Physics-Based Deep Learning for Improved Accelerated Image Reconstruction

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Motivation: Physics-based deep learning has been increasingly applied to MRI image reconstruction to accelerate acquisitions.

Goal(s): Here, we investigate whether including a relaxometry model into these networks enables higher quality accelerated reconstructions, and consequently more accurate quantitative maps.

Approach: Two recurrent inference machines with different physics models were implemented: (1) reconstruction of image series and (2) direct T2 map estimation, from undersampled k-space data.

Results: Including relaxometry into physics-informed networks improves reconstruction and T2 map quality for acceleration factors as high as 8-fold.

Impact: Integrating relaxometry models into physics-informed deep learning-based image reconstruction methods enables high quality quantitative mapping directly from undersampled k-space data, from which contrast-weighted images can also be accurately synthesised.

Introduction [123]

Physics-based deep learning has been successfully applied to MRI image reconstruction from undersampled k-space, further pushing acceleration rates¹⁻³ Here, we investigate whether including quantitative MR parameter mapping into the forward model results in higher quality reconstructions, and consequently more accurate quantitative maps, compared to networks tasked solely with reconstruction followed by a fitting step. Two recurrent inference machines (RIMs) were implemented: a RIM tasked with reconstructing a complex dynamic T2-weighted image series; and PENGUIN (PhasE graph sigNal and Gradients QUantitative Inference MachiNe), a RIM coupled with a signal evolution curve look-up table to accelerate mapping, tasked with obtaining a T2 map directly from undersampled k-space data. The image series and T2 maps obtained using the two approaches were compared using MRI brain data.

Methods [487]

Networks: The RIM was implemented considering the forward model:

$$d = \sum_{c=1}^C UFS_c s,$$

where E is the measured k-space data, s the complex image series signal, ignoring the underlying relaxometry model, C the number of coils, S the coil sensitivity matrix, F the Fourier Transform, and U the undersampling operator. PENGUIN⁴ was extended to estimate T2 maps directly from undersampled k-space following:

$$d = \sum_{c=1}^C UFS_c E(T_2),$$

where “EPG” denotes the pre-calculated look-up table of complex signal curves following the Extended Phase Graph framework considering the T_2 value for each pixel (values ranging 0 to 2000 ms) according to the acquisition protocol below. Both networks follow the architecture shown in Figure 1. At each optimization step, both perform $J=6$ inference steps to obtain 6 estimates of the target variable \hat{p} , which can either be an image series or a T2 map. The loss function was:

where L_1 is the L1-norm loss. At each step j , the network receives the current estimate \hat{p}_j , a data consistency term, comparing the estimated k-space (obtained by applying the forward model to \hat{p}_j) and the measured k-space data, and two vectors of memory states, and outputs the incremental update to the estimate Δp_j and the updated memory states. All networks were implemented with PyTorch

$$\Lambda^{\text{total}} = \frac{1}{J} \sum_{j=1}^J 10^{-\frac{J-j+1}{J-1}} \mathcal{L}_1(p, \hat{p}),$$

1.10.2, trained on an NVIDIA TESLA P100 GPU, and tested on an Intel Core i7 2.8 GHz CPU.

Data & Protocol: Networks were trained and validated with simulated images from BrainWeb⁵, following a multi-echo spin-echo acquisition sequence with 12 echoes, TE=10:10:120 ms, flip angle = [180°, 160°, ..., 160°], considering 2 simulated coil sensitivity maps placed along the anterior-posterior direction. Training data consisted of 2D randomly picked slices from 10 distinct subjects to which Gaussian noise with variance sampled from a uniform distribution was added to obtain images with SNR ranging 15 to 80 dB, totalling 2000 training images for RIM and 3000 training images for PENGUIN; validation data consisted of 5 2D slices each for another distinct subject, for SNR = {15, 30} dB and noiseless data. Separate data was generated for acceleration factors 2x, 4x, and 8x, considering a radial k-space trajectory with golden angle increments between echoes and shots.

Evaluation: In addition to RIM and PENGUIN, reconstructions were performed with Zero-Filling (ZF). The estimated T2 maps with ZF and RIM were obtained through dictionary matching, by calculating the dot product between the signal evolution curves produced by each method with each pre-calculated signal in the EPG look-up table and taking the T2 that resulted in a higher dot product for each pixel. The estimated T2 maps with PENGUIN were converted into T2-weighted images by applying the forward EPG model. T2 maps and image series were compared visually and by calculating the error and the Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) with the respective ground-truth.

Results [82]

PENGUIN provides more accurate images (Figures 2, 4) and T2 maps (Figures 3, 4) than RIM for 2x, 4x, and 8x acceleration factors. RIM and PENGUIN perform similarly when performing T2 mapping from measurements with varying SNRs, but PENGUIN is more robust to increased acquisition noise when performing image reconstruction (Figure 5).

Conclusion [58]

PENGUIN, which includes relaxometry information into RIMs, provides T2 maps directly from (up to 8-fold) undersampled k-space data that are more accurate than those obtained from the T2-weighted image series generated with RIMs. Pushing for higher acceleration factors is likely to require more complex networks hindering network optimization; it remains to be seen whether a deeper network would be able to push acceleration factors while maintaining an advantage over equivalent methods lacking MR relaxometry modelling.

References

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Figure 1. RIM and PENGUIN architectures drawn for the inference step j . \hat{p}_j consists in the estimated reconstructed image series in the RIM case, and in the estimated T2 map in the PENGUIN case. The real and imaginary parts of each input variable were separated, processed using two separate recurrent neural networks (RNNs), and combined at the end into a complex estimate.

Figure 2. a) Ground-truth and reconstructed image series for acceleration factors 2, 4 and 8, from noiseless k-space data, with ZF, RIM, and PENGUIN methods. b) Absolute difference between ground-truth and image series reconstructed from 2, 4, 8, undersampled k-space data, with ZF, RIM, and PENGUIN methods. PENGUIN generates T2 maps directly from the undersampled k-space data, yet it enables the generation of high-quality T2-weighted image series. Reconstructed echoes are shown sequentially in the animation.

Figure 3. a) Ground-truth and estimated T2 maps for acceleration factors 2, 4 and 8 from noiseless k-space data, with the zero-filled, RIM, and PENGUIN reconstruction methods. b) Absolute difference between the estimated T2 maps and ground-truth maps for acceleration factors 2, 4 and 8 from noiseless k-space data, with the zero-filled, RIM, and PENGUIN methods. PENGUIN provides T2 maps with the lowest error.

Figure 4. (left) Absolute value of the error in the grey matter and white matter regions of the estimated T2 maps and reconstructed image series on all noiseless validation images obtained with the zero-filled, RIM, and PENGUIN methods, for acceleration factors 2, 4, and 8; (right) Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) score calculated on the same images (whole brain).

Figure 5. (left) Absolute value of the error in the grey matter and white matter regions of the estimated T2 maps and reconstructed images on all validation images obtained with the zero-filled, RIM, and PENGUIN methods from 8x undersampled k-space data with SNR= {15, 30}, and noiseless data; (right) SSIM scores calculated on the same images (whole brain).

